

Exploring the Bases of Holistic Education

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ABSTRACT

The term 'Holistic Education' is quite popular in the sector of education. But it is much difficult to define it in one line. Ron Miller and John Miller, who were the main proponents of the holistic education movement, tried to classify and conceptualize this term. John Miller published 'The Holistic Curriculum' in 1988 in Canada, which was the first rational as well as methodical account of Holistic Education. In 1990, Ron Miller published 'What are School for? Holistic Education in American Culture', which may be called the pioneer book of Holistic Education. Holistic Education has focused on creating new learners' community who will be connected mentally with this planet. It has not focused on self but nurturing the students that they can reach beyond self realization. Then they can make relationship with larger community, nation, planet and the universe (Vengopal & Kumari, 2010). In this paper, the present researcher tried to discover afresh the bases of holistic education from the existing related literature. In doing this, extensive exploration was done through content analysis method and then seven bases namely, a) Community / Global Connectedness b) Emotional Stability c) Education on Democracy d) Value based Learning e) Peace Education f) Learning of Social Responsibility g) Compassion/Empathy were identified and discussed thoroughly in this paper.

Keywords: Exploration, Bases, Holistic Education

INTRODUCTION

Education is no longer just about learning tangible and measurable skills. Our past educational paradigms relied on the 'average' measurements and standardization. Children were prepared to memorize information and then take placement examinations. But a holistic approach motivates children to learn about a subject in deep. It installs curiosity and allows children to learn naturally and creatively. It is also accustomed to each child's individual persona and learning style, in contrast of the current mass educational system. The biggest benefit of a holistic approach isn't just about mental development, but it encompasses psychological, social and emotional growth. Holistic education movement kept its footstep in the late 1970s from the members of holistic education group, namely, Theodore Roszak, George Leonard, Joseph Pearce, Beverly Galyean, Jack Canfield, James Fadiman, among others. So, we can say that, Holistic education network is created by them (Miller, 1990). According to Ron Miller (1990), Holistic Education is a new paradigm of philosophy of education. It is based on the principle that every individual find out his identity, connotation and rational in life himself. It is a bridge which connects every person's life to the community, to the natural world, and to spiritual values like compassion, empathy and peace. He said, a "holistic conception of education recognizes wholes within wholes – that is, it strives for the integration and meaning at each level of organization" (Miller, 1990).

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Rudge (2008) have studied on analysis of holistic education and its pedagogical application. Considering four schools, he found three schools systems believe on the idea of holistic education and practically they have used that but the other does not believe on holistic view and principle. Actually, the last one does not believe on philosophical ideas of holistic education. However, that school fosters humanistic based values and principles. Neves (2009) have analyzed holistic approach to the Ontario Curriculum. He found that successfulness of holistic approach is depending on the authenticity and full engagement of the teacher. It is also that holistic educational curriculum helps to improve learners' own compassion and self empowerment.

Kumari (2012) studied the Bhagwad Gita in the light of holistic education. She explored the concept of holistic education in Bhagwad Gita and differences or similarities between them. The balance between spiritual, cultural and social contexts was established by her. Some of the inherent values or bases like spirituality, universal reality, meditation, knowledge of self, learning, intelligence were determined. Three basic principles, namely competitive eligibility, ecological literacy and lifelong optimal learning were explored by Grant (2017) to explain holistic educational thought in K-12 schools. According to him holistic educational thought is a journey of beauty and enlighten. In a concise study Satris (2016) analyzed construction and validation of a holistic education school evaluation tool for Montessori Erdkinder School.

Thomas (2017) found the involvement of holistic education has an impact on social value, economic value, hedonistic value and health value. In a quite similar study like the present researcher, Dey (2017) analyzed the influence of organizational and management patterns of Maharishi Vidya Mandir schools on students' academic achievement. The holistic development played an essential role for learner's academic achievement was re-established by him in his study.

RESEARCH QUESTION OF THE STUDY

What are the bases of Holistic Education?

RESEARCH OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

To explore the bases of Holistic Education

METHODOLOGY

Various preliminary bases of holistic education were derived and found from existing literature and review of related literature. The present researcher reviewed those literatures extensively and identified & derived some of the characteristics or bases of holistic education afresh. As per the essence of qualitative research, content analyses were followed thoroughly. All the requisite characteristics or bases are analyzed as code including both open codes and in-vivo codes and from those codes some final bases were derived.

FINDINGS

From the analyses of qualitative data on bases of Holistic Education, the following findings were revealed, which were triangulated and supported by the existing literatures also. Here seven dominant bases of identified and derived by the existing literatures through the process of content analysis by the present researcher.

- ***Bases of Holistic Education***
 - (a) Community / Global Connectedness
 - (b) Emotional Stability

- (c) Education on Democracy
- (d) Value based Learning
- (e) Peace Education
- (f) Learning of Social Responsibility
- (g) Compassion/Empathy

The herewith table (Table 1) presents the requisite codes, including both open codes and in-vivo codes, which were generated through content analysis of the bases of holistic education.

Table-1: Derived Preliminary Bases (Codes) and Final Bases (Categories) for Holistic Education

Derived Preliminary Bases (Codes)	Derived Final Bases (Category)
Connection with the Country	Community/ Global Connectedness
Connection with the World	
Connection with large Community	
Connection with Planet and Universe	
Their place in the World	
Participate in shaping the World to make beautiful	
Global Citizenship	
Connection with the Community	
Emotional	Emotional Stability
Psychological	
Self awareness	
Time management skill	
Emotional Balance	
Balance between Individual & Social learning	
Health Consciousness	
Individual Freedom	Education on Democracy
Good student & Citizen	
National prosperity	
Principles of Freedom	
Democracy	
Freedom of Choice	
Creativity	
Participatory Democracy	
Culture created & changed by People	
Efficiency in Management	

Derived Preliminary Bases (Codes)	Derived Final Bases (Category)
Morality	Value based Learning
Aesthetic	
Spiritual	
Value based Learning	
Spiritual life	
Integrity	
Spiritual Value	
Character building	
Meaning & purpose of Life	
Peace	
Loving Heart	
Culture of Peace	
Sustainable Culture	
Central role of Experience	
Act of Nonviolence	
Direct engagement with Environment	
Social Responsibility	Learning of Social Responsibility
Social skills	
Learning and assessment	
Relationship with Nature	
Ecological dimension	
Educating for Human development	
Compassion	Compassion/Empathy
Honouring students as individuals	
Intuitive Thinking	
Identity	
Scientific understanding	
Individual Happiness & Satisfaction	

DISCUSSION

The present researcher studied the available literature and concluded the under mentioned bases of holistic education through content analysis. The derived bases of holistic education are Community/Global Connectedness, Emotional Stability, Education on Democracy, Value based Learning, Peace Education, Learning of Social Responsibility, and Compassion/Empathy. These bases or thematic categories were developed (Table 1) from the identified codes which is discussed in this section.

- (a) **Community/Global Connectedness** – This category was developed based on the resulting codes like ‘Connection with the Country’, ‘Connection with the World’, ‘Connection with large community’, ‘Connection with Planet and Universe’, ‘Their place in the World’, ‘Participate in shaping the world to make beautiful’, ‘Global citizenship’ and ‘Connection with the community’ (Table 1). All these codes are the characteristics of holistic education derived from the existing literature. So many literatures suggested that holistic education is the medium of connection with the community or large community or country or with the world. The global citizenship is also reminded us the ‘*Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam*’ of Maha Upanishad, which means ‘The world is our Family’.
- (b) **Emotional Stability** – This category was developed based on the characteristics like ‘Emotional’, ‘Psychological’, ‘Self awareness’, ‘Time management skill’, ‘Emotional balance’, ‘Balance between individual and social learning’ and ‘Health consciousnesses’ (Table 1). Here the ‘self’ was prioritized of the students. From the literature it was found by the researcher that emotional balance, balance between self and society, awareness of self including health was talked about by the educationists or by the philosophers. Combining all these codes or characteristics the category of ‘Emotional Stability’ was devised by the researcher.
- (c) **Education on Democracy** – The derived codes like ‘Individual freedom’, ‘Good student and citizen’, ‘National prosperity’, ‘Principles of freedom’, ‘Democracy’, ‘Freedom of choice’, ‘Creativity’, ‘Participatory democracy’, ‘Culture created by people and changed by people’ and ‘Efficiency in management’ were generated (Table 1) from the literature review, which consisted this category. Democracy is one of the key topics for any education to be completed. Although democracy is an all-pervasive concept, it is found to rest ultimately on two fundamental values: equality and freedom. For holistic education also it was found that importance were given by many on freedom of choice, creativity, principles of freedom, participatory democracy or in efficiency on managements. This resultant category was very common yet powerful base of holistic education.
- (d) **Value based Learning** – Value provides a framework, a guide, and the rails of purposeful, quick and efficient movement through life. A value-driven person’s life is neither a seesaw nor does its movement resemble driftwood. The value based education or value based learning or simply value education is now very common feature of quite all of the academic and professional curricula. Here also the present researcher found profound evidences about criteria of values in the holistic education system. Morality, character building, spiritual value, meaning and purpose of life, aesthetics, spiritual life and integrity are all the pillars of value education. The category, Value based Learning, was consisted of nine codes namely, ‘Morality’, ‘Aesthetic’, ‘Spiritual’, ‘Value based learning’, ‘Spiritual life’, ‘Integrity’, ‘Spiritual value’, ‘Character building’ and ‘Meaning and purpose of life’ (Table 1).
- (e) **Peace Education** – Peace education is always part of pedagogical concepts because peace as a norm is one aspect of every valid ideal conception of society. It is one of the areas of education and conflict relationships in which there is a substantial amount of literature. It is a holistic approach and crucial indication to education that seeks to shape individual and societies. In this case many attributes were derived (Table 1) including ‘Peace’, ‘Loving heart’, ‘Culture of peace’, ‘Sustainable culture’, ‘Central role of experience’, ‘Act of nonviolence’ and ‘Direct engagement with environment’. All of these are of facet of peace education. The holistic education is expected to be fulfilled by these aspects.
- (f) **Learning of Social Responsibility** – Social responsibility in education is a process whereby it transmits appropriate values, traditions, skills and cultural norms to the next generation. Service learning promotes good deeds and academic success. To find out the bases behind the holistic education, the Learning of Social Responsibility was also worth mentioning. In justifying the base

with respect to holistic education, the outlooks (Table 1) were as follows, 'Social responsibility', 'Social skills', 'Learning and assessment', 'Relationship with nature', 'Ecological dimension' and 'Educating for human development'. All of these characteristics are derived from the existing literature only.

- (g) Compassion/Empathy** – A better understanding of the perspective of others gives us the opportunity to practice compassion/empathy in our daily life. Compassion is like a muscle, it gets stronger the more it is practiced. Our educational system understands the need for additional training in empathy and compassion, which is an exciting path for the next generation. In this study this 'Compassion or Empathy' category was developed by the combined codes of 'Honouring students as individuals', 'Compassion', 'Intuitive thinking', 'Identity', 'Scientific understanding' and 'Individual happiness and satisfaction' (Table 1).

CONCLUSION

This study aimed at investigating the bases of holistic education from the existing literature and reviews of related literatures. The findings are very mesmerizing and fruitful. There is an ancient saying that says: "*Swadeshe pujuryate raja, vidwan sarvatra pujuryate*" which means - A king is honoured in his own country whereas an educationist is honoured everywhere. Indeed, Education is universal. It goes beyond the boundaries of nation, religion, race, culture, gender and various others identifications. Today, one of the main problems in the world is identification. Children have given a particular set of ideas and have not been made to open up to new ideas, not open to the rest of the world. With this they grow up thinking only they are correct, only they are right. Knowledge and spiritual awareness should go hand in hand with social and political system. Only then can justice prevail in the society and there be a sense of belongingness with everyone in the world, irrespective of their religious and cultural background or age group. We need to impart this education – at the levels of schools and colleges.

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